

The background of the cover is a composite image. On the left, there is an aerial photograph of a river winding through a dry, brown landscape. On the right, there is a dark blue background with a white line graph showing fluctuating data points, overlaid with a faint grid pattern.

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**INNOVATIVE
APPROACHES TO
WATER RESOURCE
MANAGEMENT IN
ARID REGIONS IN THE
CONTEXT OF
CLIMATE CHANGE**

PROCEEDINGS
(Conference Proceedings)

May 19, 2026

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

WICAR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO
WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT
IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT
OF CLIMATE CHANGE**

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

May 19, 2026
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

INTERNATIONAL PROGRAM COMMITTEE

Chairman:

Umarov A.A. First Vice-Rector for Academic Affairs, UWED

Vice Chairman

Dadabaev T. Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation, UWED

Deputy Chairs:

Raimova G. M. Professor, Head of Department, UWED

Rasulov A. S. Professor, UWED

Seytov A.J. Professor, UWED.

Program Committee Members:

Rasulov A. S. Professor, UWED

Seytov A.J. Professor, UWED.

Dalabaev U. Professor, UWED

Umarova Sh. Dotsent, UWED

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Chairman:

Djalalov M.M. Vice-Rector for Digital Transformation and Economy, UWED

Deputy Chairs:

Raimova G. M. Head of the Department of System Analysis and Mathematical Modelling, UWED

Seytov A.J. Professor, UWED.

Organizing Committee Members:

Abdullaev E.E. (Dean, UWED, Uzbekistan)

Dalabaev U. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova M. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

Umarova Sh. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

CONFERENCE SECRETARIAT

Umarova Sh.G. (Head of the Secretariat), Buriev A., Kasimova N.J., Maraimova K. Sh., Khasanova D.R., Yarashev I., Solaeva M., Mustafakulova A. Kh., Akabirkhodjaeva D.R.

International Scientific and Practical Conference -2026

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference innovative approaches to water resource management in arid regions in the context of climate change on May 19, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The conference aims to discuss key issues of effective water resource management in arid regions under climate change, develop and apply innovative approaches and mathematical and computational modeling methods, share recent research results and practical experience, and strengthen international academic cooperation in this field.

Key Themes of the Conference:

1. Water Diplomacy and Integrated Approaches in International Relation: Interdisciplinary Approaches to Sustainable Development, Communication and Global Security

- Issues of systemic analysis in international relations and world politics in the context of water diplomacy
- Economic, environmental and energy aspects of sustainable development
- Systemic approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

2. Mathematical and computer modeling of optimal water resources management under climate change

- Optimal water resource management under climate change
- Modeling water resource dynamics and climate variability
- Methods of applied and computational mathematics in irrigation system modeling.

3. Environmental and Hydrogeological Processes in the Aral Sea Region: Analysis Based on Modern Technologies

- Analysis of hydrogeological processes in the Aral Sea region
- Application of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data technologies to environmental challenges
- Simulation and stochastic modeling of environmental and hydrogeological processes in the Aral region.

The event was conducted in a hybrid format with participation in English, Russian, and Uzbek. The conference provided a high-level platform for scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dinamik sistemalarning boshlang'ich tushunchalari (Qo'zg'almas nuqta haqidagi teoremaning davriy nuqtalar uchun tadbiri va uning misollardagi tahlillari)

Solayeva Mehribon Norimonovna¹, G'aniyev Asrorbek Barhayot o'g'li¹,
Xayrullayev Ne'matulla O'rinboy o'g'li¹

¹ Jahon iqtisodiyoti va diplomatiya universiteti

e-mail: m.solayeva@uwed.uz¹

Qo'zg'almas nuqta haqidagi teorema.

Qo'zg'almas nuqta deb $F(x_0) = x_0$ shartini qanoatlantiradigan x_0 nuqtaga aytiladi. E'tibor bering, $F^2(x_0) = F(F(x_0)) = F(x_0) = x_0$ va umuman olganda, $F^n(x_0) = x_0$. Shunday qilib, qo'zg'almas nuqtaning orbitasi x_0, x_0, x_0, \dots ko'rinishidagi o'zgarmas ketma-ketlikdan iborat. [3, 4]

Oraliq qiymat haqidagi teorema (The Intermediate Value Theorem). Faraz qilaylik, $F: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ funksiya uzluksiz bo'lsin. y_0 qiymati $F(a)$ va $F(b)$ orasida yotsin. U holda $[a, b]$ intervalida shunday x_0 nuqta mavjudki, unda $F(x_0) = y_0$ bo'ladi.

Soddaroq aytganda, bu teorema bizga uzluksiz funksiya $[a, b]$ intervalida $F(a)$ va $F(b)$ orasidagi barcha qiymatlarni qabul qilishini aytadi. Buning bevosita natijasi quyidagicha:

Qo'zg'almas nuqta haqidagi teorema (Fixed Point Theorem). Faraz qilaylik, $F: [a, b] \rightarrow [a, b]$ funksiya uzluksiz bo'lsin. U holda $[a, b]$ oraliqda F uchun kamida bitta qo'zg'almas nuqta mavjud.

Jalb qilish va Itarish (Attraction and Repulsion)

Qo'zg'almas nuqtalarning bir-biridan keskin farq qiluvchi ikki turi mavjud: **jalb qiluvchi** va **itaruvchi** qo'zg'almas nuqtalar.

Ta'rif. Faraz qilaylik, x_0 nuqta F funksiya uchun qo'zg'almas nuqta bo'lsin. U holda:

- Agar $|F'(x_0)| < 1$ bo'lsa, x_0 **jalb qiluvchi (attracting)** qo'zg'almas nuqta deyiladi.
- Agar $|F'(x_0)| > 1$ bo'lsa, x_0 **itaruvchi (repelling)** qo'zg'almas nuqta deyiladi.
- Nihoyat, agar $|F'(x_0)| = 1$ bo'lsa, qo'zg'almas nuqta **neytral** yoki **befarq (indifferent)**

deb ataladi.

Misol: Quyidagi funksiyani barcha qo'zg'almas nuqtalarni toping va ularni tortuvchi (attracting), itaruvchi (repelling) yoki neytral turlarga ajrating.

$$F(x) = x^2 - \frac{x}{2}$$

Yechish: Ushbu misolni yechish uchun eng avva oldingi [3, 4] maqolalarda tahlil qilib o'tganimiz kabi qo'zg'almas nuqtalarni topib olamiz, buning uchun $F(x_0) = x_0$ tenglama yechimini topamiz.

$$x^2 - \frac{x}{2} = x \Rightarrow x^2 - \frac{3x}{2} = 0$$

$$x \left(x - \frac{3}{2} \right) = 0 \Rightarrow x_1 = 0, x_2 = \frac{3}{2}$$

Ko'rinib turibdiki berilgan funksiyaning ikkita qo'zg'almas nuqtalari mavjud bo'lib, endi biz ushbu nuqtalarni itaruvchi yoki jalb qiluvchiligini yuqoridagi teoremdan aniqlaymiz, ya'ni berilgan funksiyadan hosila olib topilgan qo'zg'almas nuqtalardagi qiymatini hisoblaymiz.

$$F'(x) = 2x - \frac{1}{2} \Rightarrow F'(0) = -\frac{1}{2} \text{ va } F'\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = \frac{5}{2}$$

Ko'rinib turibdiki ushbu qiymatlardan berilgan funksiyaning 1- qo'zg'almas ya'ni nol nuqtasi jalb qiluvchi va ikkinchi qo'zg'almas nuqtasi itaruvchi ekan.

Davriy nuqtalar

Qo'zg'almas nuqtalar kabi, davriy nuqtalar ham **tortuvchi** (attracting), **itrivchi** (repelling) yoki **neytral** turlarga tasniflanishi mumkin. Bu yerdagi matematik hisob-kitoblar faqat bir oz murakkabroq, xolos. Ya'ni oldingi [2] maqolada ta'kidlab o'tganimizdek tub davri n ga teng bo'lgan davriy nuqtalarni topish uchun $F^n(x_0) = x_0$ tenglama yechimini topish kerak. Agar bu tenglamaning yechimlari to'plamini topa olsak u holda yuqoridagi ta'rifga asosan har bir davriy nuqtalarning tortuvchi yoki itaruvchiligini topish mumkin. Masalan $F(x) = x^2 - 1$ funksiyasi $0, -1, 0, -1, \dots$ orbitasiga ega bo'lgan 2-davrlil tortuvchi siklga ega.

Buni aniqlash uchun yuqorida ta'kidlab o'tganimiz kabi $F^2(x) = (x^2 - 1)^2 - 1 = x^4 - 2x^2$ funksiyasining grafigini o'rganamiz. E'tibor bering, F^2 funksiyasi to'rtta qo'zg'almas nuqtaga ega: bular F ning ikkita qo'zg'almas nuqtasi, shuningdek, 0 va -1 davriy nuqtalaridir. F^2 ning hosilasi, ya'ni $4x^3 - 4x$, ham 0 da, ham -1 da nolga teng bo'lishiga e'tibor bering, ya'ni $(F^2)'(0) = (F^2)'(-1) = 0$.

Bu shuni ko'rsatadiki, ushbu ikki nuqta F ning ikkinchi iteratsiyasi uchun tortuvchi qo'zg'almas nuqtalar hisoblanadi. Ya'ni, F^2 iteratsiyasi ostida 0 yoki -1 yaqinidagi nuqtalarning orbitalari shu nuqtalarga intiladi. Biroq, F iteratsiyasi ostida, bu orbitalar 2-davrlil siklga yaqinlashgani sayin u yoqdan-bu yoqqa (oldinga va orqaga) almashinib turadi.

Misol: Ushbu $F(x) = \frac{\pi}{2} \cos x$ funksiya uchun nol nuqtasi davriy orbitada yotadi. Ushbu orbitani tortuvchi, itaruvchi yoki neytral turga ajrating.

Yechish: Ushbu funksiyaning eng avval ikkinchi davriy nuqtalari to'plamini aniqlab olamiz, buning uchun $F^2(x) = \frac{\pi}{2} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \cos x\right)$ ikkinchi iteratsiya funksiyasini x ga tenglashtirib quyidagi tenglamaning yechimini topish lozim.

$$\frac{\pi}{2} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \cos x\right) = x$$

Avvalo ushbu tenglamaning grafik tahlilini ko'rib chiqsak,

Grafikdan ko'rinib turibdiki berilgan funksiyaning ikki davriy nuqtalari 3 ta ekan. Ya'ni $x_1 = 0$, $x_2 = \frac{\pi}{2}$, $x_3 = 0,9045$ bo'lib, endi huddi yuqoridagi kabi ushbu funksiyaning ikki davriy nuqtalarining tortuvchi yoki itaruvchi ekanligini aniqlab chiqamiz. Buning uchun tabiiy ravishda $(F^2)'(x_0)$ ni tekshiramiz.

$$(F^2)'(x_0) = \frac{\pi}{2} \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \cos x\right) \cdot \frac{\pi}{2} \sin x = \frac{\pi^2}{4} \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \cos x\right) \cdot \sin x \Rightarrow$$

$$(F^2)'(0) = 0, (F^2)'(\frac{\pi}{2}) = 0, (F^2)'(0,9045) \approx 0,8176$$

Ushbu qiymatlardan ko'rinadiki berilgan funksiyaning barcha ikkinchi davriy nuqtalari tortuvchi bo'lar ekan.

Ushbu g'oyalar bizni tortishish va itarilish ta'riflarini tabiiy ravishda davrlarga kengaytirishga undaydi: n -davrlar nuqta, agar u F^n uchun tortuvchi (itruvchi) qo'zg'almas nuqta bo'lsa, **tortuvchi (itruvchi)** davriy nuqta hisoblanadi. Bu darhol davriy orbitalar ham tortuvchi, ham itruvchi nuqtalarni o'z ichiga olishi mumkinmi degan savolni keltirib chiqaradi. Quyida ko'rib chiqishimizcha, matematik hisob-kitoblar buning iloji yo'qligini ko'rsatadi.

n -davrlar x_0 nuqtasi tortuvchi yoki itruvchi ekanligini aniqlash uchun biz F^n ning x_0 nuqtasidagi hosilasini hisoblashimiz kerak. F ning n -chi iteratsiyasi (bu F ning n -chi darajasi emas) uchun hosila hisoblashda zanjir qoidasidan foydalanish talab etiladi. Matematik analizdan bizga ma'lumki, agar F va G differensiallanuvchi funksiyalar bo'lsa, u holda ularning kompozitsiyasi hosilasi quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$(F \circ G)'(x) = F'(G(x)) \cdot G'(x)$$

Xususan,

$$(F^2)'(x_0) = F'(F(x_0)) \cdot F'(x_0) = F'(x_1) \cdot F'(x_0)$$

va

$$(F^3)'(x_0) = F'(F^2(x_0)) \cdot (F^2)'(x_0) = F'(x_2) \cdot F'(x_1) \cdot F'(x_0)$$

Zanjir qoidasini $n-1$ marta qo'llash orqali quyidagini topamiz:

Faraz qilaylik, x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} nuqtalar F funksiyasining n davrlar siklida yotsin va $x_i = F^i(x_0)$ bo'lsin. U holda:

$$(F^n)'(x_0) = F'(x_{n-1}) \cdot \dots \cdot F'(x_1) \cdot F'(x_0)$$

E'tibor bering, ushbu formula bizga F^n ning x_0 nuqtasidagi hosilasi shunchaki orbitadagi barcha nuqталarda olingan F hosilalarining ko'paytmasiga teng ekanligini aytadi. Bu shuni anglatadiki, biz avval F^n uchun umumiy formulani hisoblab o'tirishimiz shart emas. Bizga faqat F ning hosilasini topish va unga mos ravishda x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} qiymatlarini qo'yib, ko'paytirish kifoya qiladi.

Misol. Ushbu $F(x) = -\frac{3}{2}x^2 + \frac{5}{2}x + 1$ funksiya uchun nol nuqta qanday davrda yotishini tekshiring va bu davriy nuqtalarni tortuvchi va itaruvchilikka tekshiring.

Yechish: $F(x) = -\frac{3}{2}x^2 + \frac{5}{2}x + 1$ funksiyasini ko'rib chiqaylik. 0 nuqtasi 3-davrlilikda yotadi, chunki $F(0) = 1$, $F(1) = 2$ va $F(2) = 0$ Bizda $F'(x) = -3x + \frac{5}{2}$, shuning uchun $F'(0) = \frac{5}{2}$, $F'(1) = -\frac{1}{2}$ va $F'(2) = -\frac{7}{2}$.

$$\text{Bundan: } (F^3)'(0) = F'(2) \cdot F'(1) \cdot F'(0) = \left(\frac{-7}{2}\right) \left(\frac{-1}{2}\right) \left(\frac{5}{2}\right) = \frac{35}{8} > 1$$

Ekanligi kelib chiqadi va nol nuqta itaruvchi tub davri uchga teng bo'lgan nuqtaligi kelib chiqadi.

Misol. Quyidagi funksiyalarning har biri uchun nol nuqtasi davriy orbitada yotadi. Ushbu orbitani tortuvchi, itaruvchi yoki neytral turga ajrating.

$$a. F(x) = -\frac{1}{2}x^3 - \frac{3}{2}x^2 + 1$$

Yechish: $F(x) = -\frac{1}{2}x^3 - \frac{3}{2}x^2 + 1$ funksiya uchun nol boshlang'ich nuqta 3 davriy siklda yotadi chunki, $F(0) = 1$, $F(1) = -1$, $F(-1) = 0$ bo'lib, nol nuqtaning orbitasi $0, 1, -1, 0, 1, -1, \dots$ endi nol nuqtaning tortuvchi yoki itaruvchiligini tekshiramiz.

$$F'(x) = -\frac{3}{2}x^2 - 3x \Rightarrow F'(0) = 0, F'(1) = -\frac{9}{2}, F'(-1) = \frac{3}{2}$$

$$(F^3)'(0) = F'(2) \cdot F'(1) \cdot F'(0) = 0 \cdot \left(-\frac{9}{2}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = 0 < 1$$

Bundan ko'rinadi boshlang'ich nol nuqta uchunchi davriy tortuvchi nuqta

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar.

- 1) Devaney, Robert L., A first course in chaotic dynamical systems: theory and experiment 1992
- 2) Rozikov U. A., Solaeva M.N., Behavior of trajectories of a quadratic operator splitted to uncountable linear operators. {it Lobachevskii Journal of Mathematics.} 2023, Vol. 44, No. 7, p. 2910-2915.
- 3) Solayeva Mehribon Norimonovna. DINAMIK SISTEMALARNING BOSHLANG'ICH TUSHUNCHALARI (QO'ZG'ALMAS NUQTA VA SIKLIK NUQTALAR) VA ULARNI MISOLLARDAGI TAHLILLARI. Latin American Journal of Education <https://lajoe.org/index.php/LAJoE/article/view/1371>
- 4) Solayeva Mehribon Norimonovna. Basic Concepts of Dynamical Systems and Their Analysis in Examples. American Journal of Applied Science and Technology (ISSN: 2771-2745). <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajast/Volume06Issue04-14>